

**GANDBOL SPORT ZALLARIDA: XAVFSIZ JISMONIY MASHQLAR VA
JAROHLARNING OLDINI OLISH**

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Annotatsiya. Gandbol inshootlari odamlarga turli xil xizmatlarni taqdim etishi; ushbu xizmatlar baquvvat va umuman sog'lom bo'lish uchun yaratilgan xizmatlarni qamrab olganligi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Gandbol markazlarini boshqarishda a'zolari har qanday sog'liqni saqlash xavfini boshdan kechirmaslik va xavfsiz muhitda xizmatlarni olish uchun gandbol zallarining ba'zilariga mos kelishi kerak standartlar va ko'rsatmalar mavjud qilishi lozim. Bundan tashqari maqolaning maqsadi xavfsiz mashqlar tartibini o'rganish va gandbol sport markazlarida shikastlanish yoki o'lim holatlarini kamaytirish uchun soha standartlari va ko'rsatmalarini belgilashdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Gandbol, Boshqaruv, Xavfsiz Mashqlar, Jarohat.

**IN HANDBALL GYMS: SAFE PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND INJURY
PREVENTION**

Abstract. Handball facilities provide different services to people; information is provided that these services include services designed for fitness and overall health. In the management of handball centers, there must be some standards and guidelines that handball halls must comply with in order to ensure that members do not experience any health risks and receive services in a safe environment. In addition, the purpose of the article is to explore safe exercise routines and establish industry standards and guidelines to reduce injury or death in handball sports centers.

Key words: Handball, Management, Safe Exercises, Injury.

**В ГАНДБОЛЬНЫХ ЗАЛАХ: БЕЗОПАСНЫЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКИЕ УПРАЖНЕНИЯ И
ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ТРАВМИРОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация. Гандбольные площадки предоставляют населению различные услуги; предоставляется информация о том, что данные услуги включают в себя услуги, предназначенные для фитнеса и общего состояния здоровья. При управлении гандбольными центрами должны существовать некоторые стандарты и рекомендации, которым

должны соответствовать гандбольные залы, чтобы гарантировать, что участники не подвергаются никаким рискам для здоровья и получают услуги в безопасной среде. Кроме того, цель статьи — изучить безопасные упражнения и установить отраслевые стандарты и рекомендации по снижению травм или смертности в спортивных центрах гандбола.

Ключевые слова: гандбол, менеджмент, безопасные упражнения, травмы.

Kirish

So'nggi yillarda gandbol xizmatlarini taklif qiladigan ob'ektlardan foydalanishning ko'payishi bilan klublar, xodimlar va daromadlar gandbol sohasida tez o'sishni qayd etdi.

Juda rivojlanib borayotgan sport va jismoniy mashqlar sohasida mijozlar ehtiyojining oshishi tufayli ob'ektlarning ishlashi uning ma'muriyati har kuni muhimroq bo'lib qoldi.

Zallarning orasida eng muhim muammolardan biri mashqlar dasturlarida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan sog'liq uchun xavflarni boshqarishdir, bu eng asosiy xizmatdir. Noto'g'ri ishlab chiqilgan dasturlar va jismoniy mashqlar paytida xavfsizlik bilan bog'liq zarur xizmatlarni taqdim etmaslik gandbol muassasasi menejerlari va xodimlarini sud jarayonlari xavfiga duchor qilishi va birinchi navbatda ularning sog'lig'iga ta'sir qilishi mumkin, shuningdek, u xizmatni vaqtincha yoki doimiy ravishda olishni istagan iste'molchilar hayotiga ta'sir qiladigan sog'liq bilan bog'liq salbiy oqibatlarni ko'rsatishi mumkin. Shuning uchun gandbol sanoatida xavfsiz jismoniy mashqlar amaliyoti va jarohatlarning oldini olishning ahamiyati aniq paydo bo'lmoqda.

Gandbol muassasalarida jismoniy mashqlar paytida yuzaga keladigan jarohatlarni o'rganadigan juda kam tadqiqotlar mavjud va ularning aksariyati faqat yuzaga keladigan jarohatlar turlarini yoki ular paydo bo'lish chastotasini aniqlaydi. Gandbol zallari sharoitida bunday jarohatlarning o'ziga xos sabablarini aniqlash muhimdir. U jarohatlarning o'ziga xos sabablarini aniqlash, bunday jarohatlarning kelajakdagi xavfini kamaytirish bo'yicha maqsadli profilaktika choralarini ishlab chiqish, shuningdek, binolarda ushbu masala bo'yicha standartlarni o'rnatish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Gandbol muassasalari menejerlari xodimlari xavfsiz mashqlar bilan bog'liq ob'ektlar siyosati va protseduralarini ishlab chiqishda yordam beradigan turli xil ko'rsatmalarga ega. Gandbol zalida ham muvaffaqiyatli jarohati xavfini kamaytirish uchun tegishli boshqaruv dasturlarini amalga oshirish kerak.

Yo'nalish va sog'liqni tekshiruvi

Orientatsiya-yo'nalish berish, rahbarlik qilish ma'nosida qo'llaniladigan tushuncha.

Gandbol muassasasida yo'nalish har bir muassasa a'zosini yoki foydalanuvchisini xavfsiz va samarali jismoniy mashqlar dasturini boshlash va ishtirok etish uchun tegishli ma'lumot va ko'rsatmalar bilan ta'minlash jarayonini anglatadi. Kamida, har qanday a'zolik shartnomasi tuzilishidan oldin sog'liqni saqlash tarixi so'rovnomasi to'ldirilishi kerak. Aksariyat hollarda, bo'lajak a'zolar sog'lig'ini baholashni yakunlamaguncha shartnomalar imzolanmasligi kerak va tibbiy ruxsatnoma talab qilinmasligi aniqlanishi kerak. Sog'liqni saqlash tarixi so'rovnomalarini barcha yangi a'zolarga qo'llash mashqlar o'zgarishini talab qilishi va shaxslarni muayyan faoliyatdan chetlashtirishi mumkin bo'lgan oldindan mavjud sharoitlarni aniqlashi mumkin. Bir a'zosi oldin gandbol muassasasida mashqlar amalda ishtirok etish uchun sog'liqni saqlash skrining jarayonini yakunlaganda, gandbol inshooti menejeri a'zoga ob'ekt haqida umumiy yo'nalishni taqdim etishi kerak. Avvalo, u malakali gandbol mutaxassisidan yuzma-yuz murojaat qilishini ta'minlash kerak. A'zolarning xilma-xilligi tufayli gandbol zallariga yangi ob'ekt va uning jihozlari haqida umumiy ma'lumot beradigan yo'nalishlarni taqdim etishi kerak.

Professional Murabbiylar

Gandbol markazlari daromadlarining 40% dan ortig'ini xizmat ko'rsatadigan xodimlariga ajratishi ushbu markazlardagi xodimlarning tashkilot muvaffaqiyatiga qanchalik tanqidiy munosabatda ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Xodimlar o'rtasida nazoratni ta'minlaydigan muassasa, gandbol markazlari va shaxsiy yoki guruh tadqiqotlari foydalanuvchilari uchun qo'llanma professional gandbol o'qituvchilariga xizmat ko'rsatadigan muhim nuqta bo'lib, ushbu mutaxassislarning tajribasi jismoniy faoliyat havzasida oqilona xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga mas'uldir. Ushbu mas'uliyat sog'liq bilan bog'liq mumkin bo'lgan favqulodda vaziyatlarda javobgarlik mas'uliyatini o'z ichiga oladi. Gandbol bo'yicha mutaxassisning ushbu ikki tomonlama roli bir xil darajada muhimdir.

Shunga ko'ra, sog'liqni saqlash va gandbol bo'yicha mutaxassislar xavfsiz jismoniy mashqlar bilan bog'liq turli xil rol va majburiyatlarini bajarish uchun zarur vakolatlarga ega bo'lishlari kerak. Gandbol sohasida bir qator sertifikat beradigan ta'lim tashkilotlari bordir. Bu har bir tashkilot samarali gandbol o'qituvchisi uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va qobiliyatlarni taqdim etishini kafolatlaydi. Biroq, oldingi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, juda kam sertifikatlash organlari aslida ushbu faoliyatga mos keladi.

Uskunalar

Ta'kidlanishicha, jarohatlar ko'pincha vazn mashqlari, guruh mashqlari va umuman yurak-qon tomir mashqlari uskunalar bilan bog'liq.

Og'irlikning tushishi natijasida eziluvchan jarohatlar barcha erkin vaznda mashq qilish amaliyotlarida keng tarqalgan, yiqilish jarohatlari guruh mashqlari mashg'ulotlari va yurak-qon

tomir uskunalarida mashq qilish amaliyotlarida tez-tez uchraydi. Ushbu jarohatlarga yugurish yo'lakchalari yoki jismoniy mashqlar to'plaridan tushish, og'irliklar va boshqa jihozlar bilan mashq qilish paytida tushish va qoqilish holatlari kiradi.

Shikastlanishning ba'zi muhim sabablari: ishlab chiqaruvchining tavsiyalariga rioya qilmaslik, jismoniy mashqlar jihozlariga yetarli darajada texnik xizmat ko'rsatmaslik va gandbol xodimlarining jismoniy mashqlar uskunalarini to'g'ri ko'rsatma va nazorat qila olmaslikdir.

Uskunalar bilan bog'liq jarohatlar yoki o'limlarning oldini olish uchun uskunaning shikastlanishi va yetishmayotgan qismlarini muntazam ravishda tekshirish va texnik xizmat ko'rsatish kerak. Uskunadan noto'g'ri foydalanish jiddiy shikast yetkazishi mumkin. Shikastlanishlar ko'pincha uskunaning funksiyalari to'g'risida bilim yetishmasligi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Sportchi a'zolariga bunday uskunadan qanday foydalanish kerakligi to'g'risida ko'rsatma berilishi shart.

Xulosa

Xavfsizlik universaldir va bir mamlakatdan boshqasiga farq qilmaydi. Sport zallarining a'zolarini xavfsiz muhit bilan ta'minlash va ularning umumiy jismoniy sog'lig'ini yaxshilash qobiliyati asosiy e'tibor markazida bo'lishi kerak. Shu o'rinda, amalga oshirish strategiyalariga nisbatan mavjud sanoat standartlaridan foydalanish kerak. Ushbu standartlar doirasida gandbol muassasasida xavfsiz jismoniy mashqlar xizmatlarini olishni istagan shaxs uchun to'g'ri, ya'ni, yo'naltirilgan bo'lishi muhimdir. Xizmatlarni oladigan insonning xavfsiz mashqlarni bajarishi uchun uning individual xususiyatlariga muvofiq yo'naltirish kerak. Bu yerda ustuvor amaliyot sog'liqni saqlash tekshiruvini o'tkazish va shaxsga mos keladigan individual mashqlar dasturini qo'llash orqali sog'liq uchun xavf omillarini aniqlashdir.

Bu nuqtada gandbol zallarining rahbarlari, yaxshi o'qitilgan va sertifikatli mavjud xodimlarni ishga olishning, shuningdek, ta'lim va sertifikatlashtirish amal haqida xabardor bo'lishi, bundan tashqari, muayyan davrlarda u o'z murabbiylarining gandbol zonasi va favqulodda vaziyatlarga javob berish bo'yicha ma'lumot holatini ichki va tashqi mashg'ulotlar bilan yangilashi kerak. Sifatli xizmat ko'rsatish yo'nalishi bo'yicha gandbol muassasasining eng muhim operatsiyasi shikastlanish va o'lim xavfini oldini olish va xavfsiz jismoniy mashqlar muhitini ta'minlashdir. Shu sababli, muassasa menejerlari xavfsiz jismoniy mashqlar va shikastlanish masalalari bo'yicha gandbol markazi bilan bog'liq standartlar va ko'rsatmalarga rioya qilishlari kerak.

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